

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 100

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 100

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 100:0 A Psalm for †Thanksgiving.</p> <p>Psa. 100:1 “Shout joyfully to the LORD, all the earth. ² “Serve the LORD with gladness; ^bCome before Him with joyful singing. ³ Know that “the LORD ¹Himself is God; It is He who has ^bmade us, and ²not we ourselves; <i>We are</i> “His people and the sheep of His pasture.</p> <p>Psa. 100:4 Enter His gates “with ¹thanksgiving <i>And</i> His courts with praise. Give thanks to Him, ^bbless His name. ⁵ For “the LORD is good; ^bHis lovingkindness is everlasting And His “faithfulness to all generations.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 100:1 מִזְמוֹר לְתוֹדָה הַרְיֵעוּ לְיְהוָה כָּל־הָאָרֶץ : ² עֲבַדוּ אֶת־ יְהוָה בְּשִׂמְחָה בָּאוּ לְפָנָיו בְּרִנָּה : ³ דַּעוּ כִּי־יְהוָה הוּא אֱלֹהִים הוּא־ עָשָׂנוּ וְלֹא [וְ] [לֹ] אֲנַחְנוּ עָמוּ וְצֹאן מִרְעִיתוֹ : ⁴ בָּאוּ שְׁעָרָיו אֶבְתוֹדָה חֲצֹרְתָיו בְּתִהְלֵה הוֹדוּ־לוֹ בְּרִכּוֹ שִׁמּוֹ : ⁵ כִּי־טוֹב יְהוָה לְעוֹלָם חַסְדּוֹ וְעַד־דָּר וָדָר אֱמוּנָתוֹ :</p>

References

Psalm 100:0

[†]Or *thank offering*

Psalm 100:1

^aPs 95:1; 98:4, 6

Psalm 100:2

^aDeut 12:11, 12; 28:47

^bPs 95:2

Psalm 100:3

¹Or *He*

²Some mss read *His we are*

^aDeut 4:35; 1 Kin 18:39; Ps 46:10

^bJob 10:3, 8; Ps 95:6; 119:73

^cPs 74:1, 2; 95:7; Is 40:11; Ezek 34:30, 31

Psalm 100:4

¹Or *a thank offering*

^aPs 95:2; 116:17

^bPs 96:2

Psalm 100:5

^{a1} Chr 16:34; 2 Chr 5:13; 7:3; Ezra 3:11; Ps 25:8; 86:5; 106:1; 107:1; 118:1; Jer 33:11;
Nah 1:7

^bPs 136:1

^cPs 119:90

Targum

Psa. 100:1 A psalm on the offering of thanksgiving. Give a shout in the presence of the LORD, all inhabitants of the earth. ² Worship in the presence of the LORD with joy; come before him with praise. ³ Make it known, for the LORD is God; he has made us and we are his, his people and the flock of his pasture. ⁴ Enter his gates with thanksgiving, his courts with praise; give thanks in his presence, bless his name. ⁵ For the LORD is good, his goodness is forever, and his faithfulness lasts for all generations.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This is the last Psalm composed by Moses. It was sung in the Temple during the Thanksgiving offering. This offering was brought to the Temple after having survived a great danger. Not a day in one's life occurs without danger. Most of the time, a person is oblivious to the dangers and that the LORD protects from hazards performing countless miracles of salvation. Therefore, today it is sung every day.

Verse five

The Psalmist calls out to the Sefirah Chesed for the LORD's lovingkindness.

For God is good; the Sefirah Chesed endures forever giving us the LORD's love, and His guiding faithfulness extends to every generation.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

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